

Simulation of Weather and Air Quality Monitoring System

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Abstract

The simulation focuses on a weather and air quality monitoring system, providing an efficient and accessible solution for real-time monitoring of indoor environmental conditions using Internet of Things (IoT) technology. The system integrates an ESP32 microcontroller, DHT22 sensors for temperature and humidity, and a potentiometer to simulate gas levels, enabling a comprehensive assessment of air quality. Remote monitoring capabilities are implemented via the Blynk platform, while online simulation using Wokwi eliminates the need for physical hardware, ensuring a cost-effective and scalable solution. This project emphasizes the importance of air quality awareness and highlights the potential of IoT in promoting health and safety. By leveraging open-source platforms, the system demonstrates how complex environmental monitoring systems can be made widely accessible. Future developments incorporating additional sensors and enhanced functionalities could further broaden its applicability, reinforcing the significance of IoT-driven air quality monitoring systems.

Index Terms

IoT, Air Quality Monitoring, ESP32, DHT22 Sensor, Blynk Platform, Wokwi Simulation, Environmental Monitoring, Indoor Air Quality, Real-Time Monitoring, Open-Source Solutions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maintaining optimal environmental conditions is crucial for ensuring health, comfort, and safety in residential, industrial, and commercial spaces [1][2]. Temperature, humidity, and air quality significantly impact human well-being, productivity, and overall indoor comfort [3]. Poor indoor air quality, often resulting from pollutants, inadequate ventilation, and fluctuating environmental conditions, can lead to adverse health effects such as respiratory issues and reduced cognitive performance [4][5]. Thus, the need for effective monitoring and management of these parameters has become increasingly important. Traditional environmental monitoring systems primarily focus on measuring basic parameters like temperature and humidity [6][7]. However, these systems often lack comprehensive air quality assessments, such as gas level indicators or qualitative evaluations of the overall air health status [8]. This gap highlights the necessity for more advanced solutions that integrate multiple environmental metrics into a cohesive monitoring framework. This research addresses these challenges by developing a simulated weather and air quality monitoring system leveraging Internet of Things (IoT) technology. The proposed system integrates a DHT22 sensor for precise temperature and humidity measurement and a potentiometer simulating a gas sensor for air quality assessment [9]. Data is displayed on an LCD, with air quality categorized qualitatively as “Good,” “Normal,” or “Bad” based on defined thresholds [10]. The system also incorporates IoT-based remote monitoring capabilities via the Blynk platform, while utilizing the Wokwi simulation environment for design and testing without requiring physical hardware [11][12].

By focusing on accessibility and functionality, the system demonstrates a cost-effective solution for environmental monitoring, suitable for a wide range of applications, including smart homes and small-scale industrial settings [13]. Furthermore, the modular design provides a foundation for future enhancements, such as the integration of additional sensors, real-time analytics, and IoT-based automation. This work underscores the potential of IoT to revolutionize environmental monitoring, making advanced air quality systems more accessible and impactful in improving health and safety standards [14][15].

II. MOTIVATION

With rapid urbanization, rising pollution, and increased time spent indoors, indoor air quality has become a critical factor for health and well-being. Poor air quality exacerbates respiratory issues, allergies, and impacts mental clarity and productivity. Traditional devices often focus on temperature and humidity but neglect vital metrics like air and gas quality.

This project addresses these gaps by developing a low-cost, comprehensive monitoring system that provides real-time feedback on temperature, humidity, and air quality. By categorizing air and gas levels as “Good,” “Normal,” or “Bad,”

it empowers users to take proactive steps, such as improving ventilation or using air purifiers, for healthier environments. Integrating IoT technology via the Blynk platform allows remote monitoring and control, making it especially valuable for urban or industrial settings. This approach highlights how smart technologies can promote safer and healthier indoor spaces

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Indoor air quality significantly affects health, comfort, and productivity, yet many residential and small-scale industrial settings lack accessible and affordable monitoring solutions. Traditional systems typically measure basic metrics like temperature and humidity but fail to assess gas levels or provide actionable feedback on overall air quality. This gap leaves users without the necessary information to address ventilation or air purification effectively. The need for a simple, low-cost system that monitors temperature, humidity, and gas levels while offering a clear air quality rating is critical, especially in urban and industrial areas. This project aims to address this need by providing an integrated, user-friendly solution that categorizes air quality as “Good,” “Normal,” or “Bad,” delivering actionable insights and enabling healthier indoor environments.

IV. OBJECTIVES

The primary objective of the **Simulation of Weather and Air Quality Monitoring System** are:

- **Comprehensive Environmental Monitoring:** This project uses a DHT22 sensor to measure and display real-time temperature (in Celsius) and humidity (in percentage) on an I2C LCD. It assesses indoor air conditions qualitatively based on these readings, classifying them as “Good,” “Normal,” or “Bad” for easy interpretation by users.
- **Air and Gas Quality Assessment:** Gas levels are assessed through a potentiometer simulating a gas sensor, providing both a qualitative rating (“Good,” “Normal,” “Bad”) and a raw analog value (0–4095). By combining air and gas assessments, the system provides an overall air quality rating of “Good Air Quality” or “Bad Air Quality” for a clear view of indoor conditions.
- **Real-Time Display, Remote Access, and Alerts:** All collected data is displayed on an I2C LCD for local monitoring, and the Blynk platform enables remote access via mobile devices. An LED alert signals “Bad” air quality, prompting users to take immediate action. These features create a practical tool for individuals and businesses to enhance indoor air quality and comfort.

By achieving these objectives, the project aims to create a robust and practical tool for individuals and small businesses seeking to improve their indoor environments and overall air quality.

V. LITERATURE SURVEY

Air pollution, a critical environmental issue impacting public health and quality of life, has been a focus of numerous research studies aimed at developing monitoring systems. Several IoT-based solutions have been proposed in the literature to address this issue by providing real-time monitoring of air quality and promoting sustainability.

In the study by [1], an IoT-based air quality monitoring system is introduced, highlighting the significance of tracking pollutants such as CO, NO₂, and SO₂. The system leverages smart sensor networks and the MQ-2 CO sensor to monitor urban and rural air quality, with real-time data displayed on both LCD screens and the web. This setup facilitates effective pollution management and raises public awareness, while the integration of an LPG sensor adds domestic use value. The study emphasizes the importance of embedded C programming in developing such systems. Additionally, cloud integration is suggested for enhanced data analysis and system improvement. Similarly, [2] focuses on the use of time-series data analysis for weather forecasting. The research employs the DHT11 sensor to gather real-time temperature and humidity data, which is then analyzed using models like ARIMA, ANN, and MLR. The ARIMA model proves most effective for weather predictions. Correlation analysis uncovers the relationships between temperature, humidity, and pressure, offering valuable insights into their interdependencies and enabling better weather forecasting accuracy. The paper by [3] delves into an IoT-based air quality monitoring system that utilizes the MQ2 sensor and ESP32 microcontroller for pollutant detection. This system not only provides real-time monitoring of temperature and humidity but also transmits data to the cloud, enabling remote access and scalability. It alerts users when pollutant levels exceed safe thresholds, contributing to public safety. The paper highlights challenges such as sensor accuracy and data transmission, recommending future improvements such as smart home integration and mobile app support. In the context of water quality monitoring, [4] proposes a real-time system to assess critical parameters like pH, turbidity, TDS, and temperature using sensors and IoT technology. The system offers continuous monitoring and smartphone notifications, making it vital for public health, especially in areas where unsafe drinking water is a concern. Testing of water samples from different sources reveals the importance of regular monitoring, even when water appears clear, as it may still pose health risks. Another study, [5], presents an IoT-based weather monitoring system that overcomes the geographic constraints and data delays of traditional systems. By integrating affordable sensors and the Blynk platform, the system enables real-time weather data collection and storage, which can be used for applications such as disaster preparedness and agricultural planning. The study stresses the role of IoT in providing real-time alerts and aiding decision-making processes for weather-related events. The research presented in [6] describes an IoT air quality monitoring system that tracks environmental parameters

like temperature, humidity, and pollutant levels. The system, using sensors such as the DHT11 and MQ135, transmits data to the cloud for analysis and provides real-time monitoring through the Blynk app. This system is particularly useful in urban areas where pollution is prevalent and promotes public health awareness. Further innovations in air quality monitoring are discussed in [7], which presents a cost-effective system employing a range of sensors to measure harmful gases, dust, and other environmental factors. The system utilizes the ESP32 microcontroller to transmit data to an IoT platform for real-time visualization. Alerts are sent when gas levels exceed safe thresholds, ensuring timely action against pollution. The study highlights the potential for future enhancements, including SMS alerts and integration into smart city projects. The paper in [8] addresses the need for low-cost indoor air quality monitoring systems, particularly for individuals concerned about indoor pollution. Using the ESP32 microcontroller and various sensors, the system monitors pollutants and transmits data to Google Sheets for visualization and real-time alerts. The study also emphasizes the system's battery efficiency and its potential for remote firmware updates, promoting public awareness and empowering users to take action against poor air quality. Lastly, [9] proposes a comprehensive IoT-based air quality monitoring system, which integrates multiple gas sensors with an Arduino controller and the ThingSpeak cloud platform. This system allows for real-time monitoring and provides historical data for analysis. Alerts are triggered when pollutant levels exceed set thresholds, ensuring timely intervention. The study concludes that such systems are essential for mitigating the impacts of air pollution, offering an effective approach to real-time environmental monitoring. Despite the advancements in environmental monitoring systems, a significant gap remains in the existing literature. Many current systems measure various environmental parameters, such as temperature, humidity, and air quality, but fail to present this data in a clear, user-friendly format with actionable insights. A key limitation is the absence of qualitative assessments of air quality, such as categorizing air and gas levels as "Good," "Normal," or "Bad." Furthermore, many systems lack remote monitoring capabilities, which limits accessibility for non-technical users and reduces the potential for proactive management of environmental conditions. This paper addresses this gap by proposing a system that not only measures multiple environmental parameters but also presents the data in an intuitive, actionable format, incorporating remote monitoring to make the data accessible to a wider audience. This approach aims to empower users to manage air quality more effectively and raise awareness of the importance of environmental monitoring.

VI. REQUIREMENT

- **Programming Environment:** Arduino IDE – used for writing, compiling, and uploading code to the ESP32 microcontroller; compatible libraries required include DHT Library for the DHT22 sensor, LiquidCrystal_I2C Library for the I2C LCD display, and Blynk Library for remote monitoring functionality. s
- **Simulation Tool:** Wokwi Platform – an online simulator for Arduino and ESP32 projects, supporting testing and demonstration without physical components, including sensors, displays, and microcontrollers.
- **Networking Library:** Wi-Fi Library – enables the ESP32 to connect to the local Wi-Fi network for data transmission to the Blynk app.
- **ESP32 Microcontroller:** Acts as the core processing unit, managing all sensor inputs and controlling outputs, such as the LED display. Additionally, it supports Wi-Fi connectivity, enabling remote data monitoring and control, as illustrated in Fig 1.

Fig. 1: ESP32 Microcontroller

- **DHT22 Temperature and Humidity Sensor:** Measures the temperature and humidity of the environment. These readings are essential for assessing air quality, with the data sent to the ESP32 for further processing as shown in fig 2. Measures the temperature and humidity of the environment. These readings are essential for assessing air quality, with the data sent to the ESP32 for further processing. Measures the temperature and humidity of the environment. These readings are essential for assessing air quality, with the data sent to the ESP32 for further processing. Measures the temperature and humidity of the environment. These readings are essential for assessing air quality, with the data sent to the ESP32 for further processing.
- **16x2 I2C LCD Display:** Used to display sensor readings in real-time, such as temperature, humidity, gas levels, and air quality assessments. The I2C interface allows for easy integration with fewer wiring connections, as shown in fig 3.

Fig. 2: DHT22 Temperature and Humidity Sensor

Fig. 3: 16x2 I2C LCD Display

- **Potentiometer (simulating Gas Sensor):** Provides a variable resistance that simulates gas levels for this project. This input is processed by the ESP32 to display qualitative assessments like "Good," "Normal," or "Bad" gas levels, as shown in fig 4.

Fig. 4: Potentiometer

- **LED:** Serves as a visual alert for poor air quality. The ESP32 controls the LED to turn on if the air quality is determined to be "Bad," signaling the need for attention, as shown in fig 5.

Fig. 5: LED

- **Breadboard and Jumper Wires:** For prototyping and connecting the various components, facilitating a temporary setup for testing.
- **Power Supply:** A suitable power source for the ESP32, ensuring the microcontroller and other components receive the necessary voltage.

By integrating these software & components, the project aims to deliver a robust system for effectively monitoring and managing indoor air quality.

VII. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for implementing Simulation of Weather and Air Quality Monitoring System involves both software and components. This project is structured to measure temperature, humidity, and gas levels to determine indoor air quality. The

ESP32 microcontroller reads data from the DHT22 sensor and a potentiometer (simulating a gas sensor) and displays the information on an I2C-connected LCD screen. The project also uses Blynk, enabling remote monitoring of these parameters.

- 1) **Setup and Initialization:** In the setup phase, the ESP32 is initialized to establish connections, as shown in Fig 6, with the DHT22 sensor, LCD display, and Blynk platform. The LiquidCrystal I2C library initializes the 16x2 LCD screen with an I2C address of 0x27. The DHT22 sensor is configured to read temperature and humidity, while the potentiometer connected to pin 34 simulates a gas sensor. The device connects to Wi-Fi using pre-defined network credentials, enabling data transmission to the Blynk app.

Fig. 6: Circuit Connection

- 2) **Data Reading and Analysis:** The ESP32 continuously reads data from the sensors. The DHT22 sensor provides temperature and humidity values, while the potentiometer generates gas level data as a raw value (0–4095) using the ESP32's ADC. The sendData() function sends these values to Blynk virtual pins V1, V2, and V3. Simultaneously, conditions are evaluated to determine air and gas levels. For example:
 - **Air Level:** Based on temperature (22–30°C for good) and humidity (30–60% for good), air quality is classified as "Good," "Normal," or "Bad."
 - **Gas Level:** The raw gas values are categorized as "Good," "Normal," or "Bad" based on specified ranges (e.g., 0–1364 for good).
 - **Overall Air Quality:** If both air and gas levels are "Good" or "Normal," the overall air quality is labeled as "Good"; otherwise, it is "Bad."
- 3) **Display and Notification:** The results are shown on the LCD screen in four stages, each displayed for two seconds:
 - **Temperature and Humidity:** The temperature (in Celsius) and humidity percentage are displayed.
 - **Air Level:** Displays the air quality level determined from temperature and humidity.
 - **Gas Level and Value:** Shows the qualitative gas level and raw gas sensor value.
 - **Overall Air Quality:** Indicates if the air quality is "Good" or "Bad."

Additionally, an LED connected to ledPin indicates poor air quality by lighting up if the overall air quality is determined to be "Bad," providing immediate, visual feedback for users in the monitored environment.

- 4) **Remote Monitoring via Blynk:** Data is sent to the Blynk app, where users can monitor the environment remotely, allowing greater flexibility in air quality management. This enhances the system's usability, making it convenient for users to track environmental conditions from any location with internet access.

This structured methodology integrates IoT capabilities with user-friendly display and monitoring functions, demonstrating an accessible and effective solution for indoor air quality management.

VIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The project, Simulation of Weather and Air Quality Monitoring System, successfully displayed real-time temperature, humidity, gas level, air level, and overall air quality on an I2C LCD screen. The system achieved its purpose of monitoring and displaying the environmental conditions effectively by using sensors and real-time feedback with Blynk for remote monitoring.

- 1) **Temperature and Humidity Monitoring:**

- The temperature and humidity values are read using the DHT22 sensor and updated on the LCD every few seconds. This enables continuous monitoring of environmental conditions.
- When temperature values are between 22°C and 30°C and humidity is between 30% and 60%, the system categorizes the air as Good.
- If temperature values range between 30°C and 40°C with humidity between 60% and 70%, the air level is identified as Normal.

- For temperature and humidity readings outside these ranges, the air level is categorized as Bad.

2) Gas Level Detection:

- Using a potentiometer as a mock gas sensor, the project determines gas levels based on analog readings.
- Gas values are categorized as Good (0–1364), Normal (1365–2730), or Bad (2731 and above).
- The LCD displays both the gas level and its value for detailed, visual feedback.

3) Air Quality Calculation:

- Based on the combined conditions of air level and gas level, the system determines whether the overall Air Quality is “Good” or “Bad.”
- The system displays “Good Air Quality” on the LCD if both air level and gas level are within the good or normal range.
- If either air or gas level is Bad, the air quality is labeled as “Bad Air Quality,” triggering an LED warning light for quick visual indication.

The system continuously monitors temperature, humidity, and gas levels to assess air quality. The DHT22 sensor reads temperature and humidity, displaying updates on the LCD, and categorizes the air as “Good,” “Normal,” or “Bad” based on predefined ranges. A potentiometer simulates gas levels (methane), which are classified as Good, Normal, or Bad, with both the gas level and its value shown on the LCD. The overall air quality is calculated by combining the air level and gas level conditions, displaying “Good Air Quality” when both are within acceptable ranges, and “Bad Air Quality” if either parameter is out of range, triggering an LED warning light for immediate alert. Table 1 summarizes the output results, detailing the relationship between temperature, humidity, gas values, and the corresponding air quality levels, providing a comprehensive overview of system performance.

Temperature (°C)	Humidity (%)	Gas Value	Air Level	Gas Level	Air Quality
22 – 30	30 – 60	0 – 1364	Good	Good	Good Air Quality
22 – 30	30 – 60	1365 – 2730	Good	Normal	Good Air Quality
22 – 30	30 – 60	> 2730	Good	Bad	Bad Air Quality
30 – 40	60 – 70	0 – 1364	Normal	Good	Good Air Quality
30 – 40	60 – 70	1365 – 2730	Normal	Normal	Good Air Quality
30 – 40	60 – 70	> 2730	Normal	Bad	Bad Air Quality

TABLE 1: Results Summary Table

For temperatures ranging from 22 to 30°C and humidity levels between 30 to 60%, a gas value (methane) between 0 and 1364 results in both good air and gas levels, leading to good air quality.

Fig. 7: Displaying Temperature (24.00°C) and Humidity (32.50%) on the I2C LCD

Fig 7, illustrates the real-time display of temperature and humidity values on the I2C LCD screen. The data is provided by the DHT22 sensor, which measures both temperature and humidity in the surrounding environment. The system continuously updates these readings on the LCD screen, allowing users to monitor the current environmental conditions. The I2C interface

simplifies the connection between the microcontroller (such as the ESP32) and the LCD, requiring fewer wires and providing efficient communication. The displayed values are updated periodically and enabling the user to easily track any changes in temperature and humidity levels. This feature enhances the functionality of the system by providing a clear, immediate visual representation of the indoor climate on the LCD screen.

Fig. 8: Displaying Air Level as Good on the I2C LCD

Fig 8, displays the air level on the I2C LCD, indicating that the air quality is categorized as "Good." This is based on the readings of temperature, humidity, and gas levels from the system. When the temperature is between 22°C to 30°C and the humidity is within the range of 30% to 60%, the system classifies the air quality as "Good." These conditions, combined with a low gas value (e.g., methane), ensure that the environment is safe and conducive for indoor living. The I2C LCD screen provides real-time updates, showing the air level status clearly, allowing users to immediately assess the quality of their indoor air. This feature is particularly valuable for maintaining optimal environmental conditions and enhancing user awareness of air quality.

Fig. 9: Displaying Gas Level (Good) and Gas Value (0) on the I2C LCD

Fig. 10: Displaying Air Quality as Good Air Quality on the I2C LCD

Fig 9, illustrates the gas level and gas value displayed on the I2C LCD, showing a "Good" gas level with a gas value of 0. The system utilizes a potentiometer to simulate the methane gas sensor, which provides analog readings corresponding to

gas concentrations. In this case, the gas value is within the range of 0 to 1364, indicating a safe, low level of gas, classified as "Good." The I2C LCD provides a clear visual display of both the gas level and its specific value, allowing users to easily monitor and assess the gas concentration in their environment. This feature helps ensure that the indoor air quality is safe, and any changes in gas levels can be detected promptly for appropriate action.

Fig 10, presents the overall air quality displayed on the I2C LCD, indicating "Good Air Quality." This is determined by the combined assessment of the temperature, humidity, and gas levels. When the temperature is between 22°C and 30°C, humidity is within the range of 30% to 60%, and the gas level falls within the "Good" range (0 to 1364), the system categorizes the air as having good quality. The I2C LCD provides a clear and real-time display of the air quality status. This functionality is crucial for monitoring air quality and ensuring a healthy, safe atmosphere for the users.

IX. CONCLUSION

The Weather and Air Quality Monitoring System project demonstrates an efficient IoT-based solution for monitoring indoor environmental conditions. By integrating an ESP32 microcontroller, DHT22 sensors for temperature and humidity, and a potentiometer to simulate gas levels, the system provides real-time air quality assessments. The inclusion of Blynk for remote monitoring and the Wokwi platform for online simulation enhances its versatility, enabling cost-effective implementation. This project raises awareness of indoor air quality and highlights the potential of IoT solutions for improving health and safety. Future expansions could include additional sensors, further enhancing its applicability in various settings.

X. FUTURE SCOPE

The future scope of this Weather and Air Quality Monitoring Display system includes several promising advancements. Firstly, replacing the potentiometer with advanced air quality sensors, such as CO₂, PM_{2.5}, or VOC detectors, could enable accurate detection of specific pollutants, thereby enhancing system reliability for monitoring air contaminants. Additionally, implementing real-time data logging and analysis via cloud storage or a local database would allow users to track historical environmental data, revealing trends and helping predict air quality fluctuations. By expanding the mobile application with enhanced Blynk functionalities, the system could send real-time notifications to alert users whenever air quality reaches unsafe levels. Incorporating machine learning algorithms could further improve predictive capabilities, enabling the system to foresee potential air quality changes based on environmental patterns and historical data, thus helping users take preemptive actions. Moreover, by adding more environmental sensors, such as barometric pressure, wind speed, and UV level sensors, the system could provide a comprehensive monitoring solution, turning it into a multi-faceted weather and environmental tool. Expanding to a portable, battery-powered design would allow users to carry the device for personal air quality monitoring, making the system suitable for both indoor and outdoor use. Integrating with smart home ecosystems, like Google Home or Alexa, would enable automated responses, such as activating air purifiers or adjusting HVAC systems in response to detected air quality declines. Finally, establishing a community-based network by deploying multiple units could facilitate collective monitoring, where local neighborhoods or cities track and share air quality data in real time, providing a low-cost, scalable solution for large-scale environmental management and raising community awareness about air quality issues. This system has immense potential to evolve into a robust tool for both personal and public health management by fostering better environmental awareness and proactive measures.

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